

Template synthesis of alkaline earth metal complexes of oxa-azamacrocycles derived from β -diketones

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Abstract : Complexes of the type $[MLCl]Cl$ (where $M = Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}$ and Ba^{II} ; $L = N_2O_3$ type macrocycle having 18-membered ring) have been synthesized by 1+1 cyclocondensation of 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and β -diketones such as 2,4-pentanedione, 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione or 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione in the presence of Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} and Ba^{2+} ions as templates. These have been characterized by elemental analyses, conductance measurements and IR, 1H NMR and FAB mass spectra.

Keywords : Macrocyclic complexes, alkaline earth metals, IR spectra, 1H NMR spectra, FAB mass spectra.

Introduction

In the last few years there has been growing interest in the chemistry of oxa-azamacrocycles on account of their unique complexation properties that are intermediate between those of the oxygen donor macrocycles i.e. crown ethers which strongly complex alkali and alkaline earth metal ions¹⁻³ and those of nitrogen donor macrocycles i.e. azamacrocycles, which bind strongly to transition metal ions⁴⁻⁶. However, oxa-azamacrocycles can form stable complexes with both alkali and alkaline earth metals as well as transition metal ions⁷⁻¹². The interest toward molecular recognition and activation of anionic or neutral substrates has led to further development in the chemistry of such macrocycles¹³⁻¹⁷. A series of oxa-azamacrocyclic complexes of transition metals have been synthesized and their biological studies have been reported earlier from our laboratories¹⁸⁻²⁰. In the present paper alkaline earth metal complexes of 18-membered oxa-azamacrocycles derived from 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and β -diketones such as 2,4-pentanedione, 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione and 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione are described.

Results and discussion

The reactions of metal chlorides with 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and different β -diketones such as 2,4-pentanedione, 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione or 1,3-diphenyl-

1,3-propanedione in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios resulted in the formation of metal complexes of 18-membered N_2O_3 macrocycles (Fig. 1). The resulting complexes were obtained as white or yellow solids. On heating they do not melt but decompose. These are insoluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and ether but soluble in DMSO. The analyses and characteristic of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. The molar conductances of the complexes indicate their 1 : 1 electrolytic nature²¹.

Infrared spectra :

The IR spectra of M^{II} macrocyclic complexes do not exhibit any band corresponding to the free primary amino ($3200-3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) or free keto group ($\sim 1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$) which suggests the complete condensation of the amino group with the keto group^{22,23}. All the complexes show a medium intensity band in the region $1580-1640\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which can be assigned to $\nu(C=N)$ ²⁴⁻²⁶. In case of the complexes of macrocycles containing phenyl groups the absorption band at 1560 cm^{-1} may be attributed to the $\nu(C=C)$ of phenyl group and a band at 760 cm^{-1} is assignable to C-H out-of-plane bending of the phenyl groups²⁷. All the complexes show bands in the region $420-460\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to $\nu(M-N)$ ²⁸.

1H NMR spectra :

The structures of the complexes of N_2O_3 macrocycles were confirmed by 1H NMR spectra. The 1H NMR spec-

Fig. 1. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes.

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of the macrocyclic complexes

Complex	Colour and decom. temp.	Yield (%)	Analyses (%) :		Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
			Found	(Calcd.)	
[Mg{(Me) ₂ [18]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl]Cl	White (189)	29	6.35 (6.40)	7.37 (7.38)	73
[Mg{(Me)(Ph)[18]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl]Cl	White (209)	35	5.46 (5.50)	6.32 (6.34)	59
[Mg{(Ph) ₂ [18]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl]Cl	Light yellow (204)	38	4.78 (4.82)	5.51 (5.56)	79
[Ca{(Me) ₂ [18]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl]Cl	White (180)	30	10.09 (10.14)	7.01 (7.08)	68
[Ca{(Me)(Ph)[18]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl]Cl	White (178)	39	8.77 (8.76)	6.09 (6.12)	79

Table-1 (contd.)

[Ca{(Ph) ₂ [18]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl]Cl	White (173)	26	7.64 (7.72)	5.35 (5.39)	62
[Sr{(Me) ₂ [18]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl]Cl	White (207)	31	19.81 (19.86)	6.28 (6.31)	71
[Sr{(Me)(Ph)[18]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl]Cl	White (210)	41	17.36 (17.42)	5.50 (5.54)	62
[Sr{(Ph) ₂ [18]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl]Cl	White (189)	34	15.49 (15.51)	4.90 (4.93)	67
[Ba{(Me) ₂ [18]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl]Cl	White (198)	31	27.93 (27.98)	5.64 (5.67)	72
[Ba{(Me)(Ph)[18]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl]Cl	White (204)	46	24.81 (24.86)	5.00 (5.04)	62
[Ba{(Ph) ₂ [18]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl]Cl	Yellow (168)	54	22.32 (22.36)	4.48 (4.53)	58

tra of two complexes [Mg{(CH₃)₂^a[18]dieneN₂O₃}Cl]Cl (I) and [Sr{(C₆H₅)₂^c[18]dieneN₂O₃}Cl]Cl (II) were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆. A peak at δ 2.49 ppm is observed in the spectra of both the complexes due to the residual methyl protons of the solvent DMSO-*d*₆. Free diamine shows a peak at δ 1.43 ppm due to -NH₂ protons which disappears in the spectra of macrocyclic complexes confirming the condensation of -NH₂ groups of the amine residue with the C=O groups of the ketone residue to give macrocycles having C=N linkages. In the spectra of macrocyclic complexes the -NCH₂ (α) and -OCH₂ protons merge together and a broad peak is observed at δ 2.77 ppm. The β -CH₂ protons of the amine residue appear as a quintet at δ 1.77 and 1.76 ppm in complexes I and II respectively due to coupling with -NCH₂ (α) and -OCH₂ protons. In 1,2,8,9-tetraphenyl-3,7-diazaduohepta-2,7-diene-1,9-dione (KIM, Fig. 2) the α -CH₂ protons have been reported to appear as a triplet at δ 3.63 ppm and β -

Fig. 2. KIM

CH₂ protons as a quintet at δ 2.11 ppm²⁹. The free macrocycles have not been isolated during the present

investigations but they are expected to exhibit the -NCH₂ (α) and β -CH₂ protons almost at the same positions as reported for KIM. As compared to KIM, in macrocyclic complexes I and II, the peaks of -NCH₂ (α) and β -CH₂ protons are observed at higher field. This high-field shift of these protons confirms the coordination of the nitrogen and oxygen atoms of the macrocycle to the metal atom.

In free 2,4-pentanedione [CH₃^aCOCH₂^bCOCH₃^a], the CH₃^a protons exhibit a singlet at δ 2.09 ppm and CH₂^b protons a singlet at δ 3.04 ppm. In the corresponding complex I, CH₃^a protons of the ketone moiety give rise to a singlet at δ 1.95 ppm and CH₂^b proton give a singlet at δ 2.71 ppm. In free 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione [C₆H₅^cCOCH₂^bCOC₆H₅^c], the C₆H₅^c protons exhibit a multiplet at δ 7.86 ppm and the CH₂^b protons a singlet at δ 3.11 ppm. In the corresponding complex II, the C₆H₅^c protons appear as a multiplet at δ 7.31 ppm and CH₂^b protons as a singlet at δ 2.59 ppm. High field shifting of these protons in both the complexes supports the coordination of C=N groups to the metal atom.

FAB mass spectra :

The FAB mass spectra of [Mg{(Me)(Ph)[18]dieneN₂O₃}Cl]Cl, [Ca{(Ph)₂[18]dieneN₂O₃}Cl]Cl and [Ba{(Me)₂[18]dieneN₂O₃}Cl]Cl have been recorded using NBA matrix. Peaks at *m/z* 136, 137, 154, 289 and 307 are due to matrix. All the complexes show peaks corresponding to molecular ions [M⁺] and free macrocycles [L⁺], which confirm the formation of the macrocyclic complexes. In all the three complexes the

peaks due to $[M+H]^+$ or $[L+H]^+$ have also been observed. In addition to the peaks due to the molecular ions and the macrocycles, the spectra exhibit peaks assignable to various fragments arising from the thermal cleavage of the macrocycles and their complexes. The fragmentation pattern for the complex $[Ca\{(Ph)_2[18]dieneN_2O_3\}Cl]Cl$ is given in Fig. 3. The complex **a** exhibits molecular ion $[M^+]$ peak at m/z 518 (9.09%) and $[M+H]^+$ peak at 519

(2.16%). Fragments **b** and **c** are formed due to the successive loss of two Cl groups from molecular ion **a** and appear at m/z 483 (6.06%) and m/z 448 (15.15%) respectively. There are two possible pathways for the fragmentation of the complex :

Pathway [A] : In this pathway, the metal ion remains attached with the macrocyclic framework and step by step loss of C_6H_5 groups from **c** gives peaks at m/z 371 (3.03%)

Fig. 3. Fragmentation pattern of $[Ca\{(C_6H_5)_2[18]dieneN_2O_3\}Cl]Cl$.

and 294 (12.12%) due to the species **d** and **e** respectively. Loss of Ca from the species **e** finally gives the species **h**, m/z 254 (7.32%).

Pathway [B] : In this pathway, the metal ion may be lost from the macrocyclic complex in the beginning and a peak at m/z 408 (4.32%) appears due to the free macrocycle **f**. Subsequent loss of C_6H_5 groups from the macrocycle gives peaks at m/z 331 (2.45%) and m/z 254 (7.32%) due to the species **g** and **h** respectively. Thus the mass spectral studies strongly support the formation of macrocyclic complexes and their structures.

Experimental

$MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Himedia), $CaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (Merck), $SrCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Merck) and $BaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (Merck) used were of A.R. grade. 1,13-Diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane (Merck), 2,4-pentanedione (Merck), 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione (Fluka) and 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione (Merck) were used as such and *n*-butanol and methanol were distilled before use. Magnesium, calcium and strontium were determined volumetrically by EDTA using Eriochrome Black T as indicator and barium was determined gravimetrically as $BaSO_4$ ³⁰. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. Conductances in DMSO were determined using Systronics Direct Reading Conductivity Meter-304. IR spectra were recorded as KBr pellets in the region 400–4000 cm^{-1} on a Shimadzu-8400 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ on a Jeol AL-300 spectrometer at 300 MHz using TMS as a reference. The FAB mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol SX 102/DA-6000 Mass Spectrometer/Data system using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas.

Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes :

(a) *Synthesis of Mg^{II} complexes of oxa-azamacrocycles :*
To a butanolic solution of $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (0.988 g, 4.85 mmol in 20 ml *n*-butanol), a butanolic solution of 2,4-pentanedione (0.486 g, 4.85 mmol in 10 ml *n*-butanol) was added. Then a solution of 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane (1.07 g, 4.85 mmol in 10 ml *n*-butanol) was added to this under continuous stirring. The contents were stirred for 6 h and the solid obtained was filtered, washed with *n*-butanol and dried *in vacuo*. Mg^{II} complex of 18-membered diazatrioxamacrocyclic was isolated. Similar method was adopted for the synthesis of Mg^{II} complexes of macrocycles derived from 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-

trioxatridecane and 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione or 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione.

(b) *Synthesis of Ca^{II} complexes of oxa-azamacrocycles :*
To a butanolic solution of $CaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (0.989 g, 6.72 mmol in 15 ml *n*-butanol), a butanolic solution of 2,4-pentanedione (0.673 g, 6.72 mmol in 10 ml *n*-butanol) was added. To this reaction mixture, a butanolic solution of 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane (1.48 g, 6.72 mmol in 10 ml *n*-butanol) was added under continuous stirring. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with *n*-butanol and dried under *vacuo*. Similar method was adopted for the synthesis of Ca^{II} complexes of macrocycles derived from 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione or 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione.

(c) *Synthesis of Sr^{II} complexes of oxa-azamacrocycles :*
 $SrCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (0.786 g, 2.95 mmol) was dissolved in minimum amount of water and 10 ml *n*-butanol. The butanolic solution of 2,4-pentanedione (0.295 g, 2.95 mmol in 10 ml *n*-butanol) was added. Then a butanolic solution of 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane (0.649 g, 2.95 mmol in 15 ml *n*-butanol) was added dropwise under continuous stirring. The stirring was continued for 10 h. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with *n*-butanol and dried *in vacuo*. Similarly, the reactions of $SrCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ with 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione or 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione were carried out and Sr^{II} complexes of 18-membered diazatrioxamacrocyclics were isolated.

(d) *Synthesis of Ba^{II} complexes of oxa-azamacrocycles :*
 $BaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (0.788 g, 3.22 mmol) was dissolved in 10 ml methanol. To this methanolic solution of 2,4-pentanedione (0.322 g, 3.22 mmol in 10 ml methanol) was added. Then 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane (0.710 g, 3.22 mmol in 10 ml methanol) was added dropwise under continuous stirring. Stirring was continued for 10 h. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with methanol and dried *in vacuo*. Similar method was adopted for the synthesis of Ba^{II} complexes of macrocycles derived from 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione or 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione.

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